

D8.2

Yearly Communication Impact Report

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Executive Summary

Communication and dissemination are a central part of the BBTWINS project to ensure that the project activities, results and technology are communicated to the relevant stakeholders in a clear, consistent and effective manner.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan (D8.1) identifies the main objectives for communicating and disseminating the BBTWINS project, the key stakeholders to be targeted, and the strategy for engaging with these stakeholders to maximise opportunities for the project results to be exploited at national and European level.

This document is an annual report tracking the communication key performance indicators and their targets. First, the tables of KPIs are displayed below, followed by the impact report. This period is for M1-M12 of the BBTINW project.

1. Overview of the Project

Bio-Based Digital Twins (BBTWINS) aims to develop a digital platform for the optimisation of agri-food value chain processes and the supply of quality biomass for bioprocessing. The platform will be based on ‘digital twins’ technology – creating a real-time digital replica of physical processes in the agri-food industry. BBTWINS will also combine Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning, the Internet of Things (IoT) and software analytics in this single platform.

With 13 partners in 7 countries, the BBTWINS consortium will be focusing on meat and fruit production, integrating the value chain (from crop to final product) and will define the optimal pathway for each feedstock to maximise efficiency and minimise losses – without impacting quality.

1.1. Introduction

The BBTWINS Yearly Communication Impact Report helps track the communication and dissemination key performance indicators (KPIs) as part of ensuring a comprehensive communication and dissemination of BBTWINS

Communicating with stakeholders is a key challenge, both to inform them on project activities and results, but also to ensure the uptake of project technology and ensure the project’s lasting impact. To facilitate this communication, the project will reach out to stakeholders through the duration of the project to raise awareness of the added value of digitalisation in agri-food value chains in achieving increased resource efficiency, as well as to highlight the potential of BBTWINS technology.

1.2. Objectives

The main aim of WP8 ‘Communication and Dissemination’ is to advance and enhance the impact and results of the BBTWINS project around Europe and beyond. To achieve this, the Communication and Dissemination plan (D8.1) puts in place a strategy to deliver project activities, engage stakeholders, and ensure the outcomes of the project are exploited. This overarching communication and dissemination plan also requires strategies for both internal and external communication.

The plan sets out a clear overview on how all communication channels, activities, and tools working together to engage with the relevant stakeholder groups (see Table 2). WP8 overlaps with all other work packages apart from WP 9 Project Management (see Figure 1).

2. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The KPIs of the BBTWINS project are there to provide direction to the communication and dissemination efforts. The KPIs listed below (Table 3) will be monitored internally, with impact reports created annually (deliverables 8.2, 8.6, 8.7 and 8.8) showing progress on reaching these KPIs (M12, M24, M36 and M48).

Table 4 - List of KPIs

<u>Dissemination Products</u>	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Press releases	2	2	2	2
Quarterly Newsletter	4	4	4	4
(# of project subscribers)	500	700	900	1200
(Opening rate per list segment)	25%	25%	30%	40%
Media Kit	1			
Press articles / media coverage	5	10	15	20
Specialised press – feature articles	1	1	1	1
(# of views / print dissemination)	100	200	300	400
Peer reviewed Open Access publications	2	2	2	2
Joint private-public publications	2	2	2	2
Videos	1			
Introductory project video	1			
Partner interviews	7	7	7	7
Use case highlight videos			2	
(# of views)	250	500	800	1000
Data visualisation and digital journey		2		2
(# of users)		100	250	400
<u>Dissemination / Clustering activities</u>				
Stakeholder consultations	2	2	2	2
Workshops				
(# of events organised per year)	1	1	1	1
(# of attendees per event organised)	50	80	100	150
(# of views per recorded webinar)	60	90	120	170
Mid-term Workshop & Results Conference			1	
(# of attendees)			150	
Final International Conference				1
(# of attendee)			150	
Event participation				
(# of conferences, workshops, pitch events, trade fairs, other)	10	10	10	10
Activities Co-organised w/ JU projects	1	1	1	1

3. Annual Impact Report Annex

Year 1 Impact Reporting

BBTWINS

Bio-based Industries Consortium

Horizon 2020
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Media Relations

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Press Releases	2			
Press articles/media coverage	20			
Specialised press/feature articles	1			

Scientific Publications

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Peer-reviewed open access publications	0			
Joint private-public publications*	0			

Events

Events
Events attended:
Workshops/conferences organised:
Events co-organised with other JU projects
Stakeholder consultations

Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
18			
1			
1			
0			

Newsletter

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Total newsletters	2			
Subscribers	102			
Opening rate	26.5%			

Videos

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Videos	2			
Total views	276			
Partner interviews	7*			

Website Overview

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Total Users	1,448			
Views	5,088			
Engagement Rate	30.41%			

Twitter

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Total Followers	104			
Impressions	10,156			
Engagement Rate*	3.6%			

*Engagement rates measure the likes, shares, and comments to evaluate content quality.

LinkedIn

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Total Followers	302			
Impressions	7,374			
Engagement Rate*	4.99%			

*Engagement rates measure the likes, shares, and comments to evaluate content quality.

